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SECURITY, STABILITY AND NATIONAL MINORITIES – A LESSON FOR UKRAINE AND THE REGION

CZU: 351.86:342.724(477)

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12754857>

Abstract

Nation state-building has led to collisions several times in the multi-ethnic region of Central and Eastern Europe. In 2014, Ukraine joined the group of states openly applying assimilatory policies, when it started to curtail the rights of national minorities by adopting laws of restrictive nature. These pieces of legislation have been criticized by international partners, including Ukraine's neighbours, and also by international organizations, like the Venice Commission; however, with no effects on Ukraine so far. On the other hand, harsh policies on national minorities served a pretext for the open Russian aggression on February 24, 2022.

In a multi-ethnic country like Ukraine, the restoration of the legislation prior to 2014 is not satisfactory, a new approach is needed. Europe has a solid knowledge on nation-state building but also on integrating national minorities into nation-states. A common experience is that individual rights are not the proper way to accommodate national minorities whom reside concentrated into a part of the nation-state. The solution might be the application of territory-based power-sharing institutions similar to Western European and Moldavian models. These institutions implemented to accommodate national minorities and to maintain the territorial integrity of the state have proven to be adequate tools to enhance social cohesion that Ukraine needs so much. The enactment of such institutions in Ukraine would result in better understanding, and would also ease international relations, limit Russia's possibilities to use minority issues as pretexts against Ukraine and strengthen regional stability and security.

Keywords: *Ukraine, minority rights, nation-building, power-sharing, legislation on minority rights*

Introduction

On September 30, 2022, the day Russia annexed the Eastern counties of Ukraine, Russian President Vladimir Putin stated that *'there is nothing stronger than the determination of millions of people who, by their culture, religion, traditions, and language, consider themselves part of Russia, whose ancestors lived in a single country for centuries. There is nothing stronger than their determination to return to their true historical homeland'*.¹ He also argued that the referenda executed a couple of days earlier in the

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¹ Signing of treaties on accession of Donetsk and Lugansk people's republics and Zaporozhye and Kherson regions to Russia 30 September, 2022, <http://en.kremlin.ru/events/president/news/69465>

occupied regions of Ukraine represented the expression of the will of the people in line with the

Article 1 of the UN Charter. This clearly is a usurpation of the right to self-determination, although application of force has resulted in its illegal implementation so far.

In this paper, we intend to present the challenges Ukraine in particular, and the region in general face if challenges related to national minorities remain unresolved and conventional nation-state building mentality continues to prevail. First, we briefly detail the process of nation-state building and its implication on minority rights. After that we address the question of comforting national minorities within nation-states. Third, we focus on the process of degrading the rights of national minorities in Ukraine, and the challenges it causes. And finally, we discuss policies on geographically concentrated ethnic minorities in Ukraine. We conclude that although assimilatory policies applied in Ukraine could be explained from historical and political perspective, they create tensions and worsen regional stability providing a fertile ground for malevolent external actors as we have been experiencing it with the ongoing Russian aggression on Ukraine.

Nation-stateness – A foundation stone of European state-building?

The idea that nations shall not be subjected to “illegitimate alien rule” became a dogma after 1789 (Connor, 1979: 25-26). It was emphasized especially by the final partition of Poland in 1795, “*the most revolutionary act of the old absolutism*”. This act divided a whole nation among its enemies and gradually awakened the theory of nationality in Europe, converting a dormant right into an aspiration, and a sentiment into a political claim (Acton, 1862). From that time, creating a nation-state has been pivotal for European nations. If achieved, the nation-state aims unification and the realization of the economic and politic domination of the centre on the entire territory of the state. From linguistic point of view, administrative control over the territories resulted in the standardization of the dominant language, a ‘common’ culture and the pressure towards linguistic homogenization (Levy, 2007: 231-233, Requejo, 2007: 12). Nation-stateness is, however, a quite recent historical phenomenon; the previous forms of political organization preceding it did not require linguistic uniformity, they were happy as long as taxes were paid (May, 2007: 127).

In a nation-state, co-citizens are assumed to share a common national identity, national language, and national public culture, all of which are reinforced by nation-building policies in the spheres of education, official languages, public media, symbols, etc. (Kymlicka, Patten, 2012: 11). Besides language, the nation-state has to decide on several crucial issues connected to identity: among others the legalization or prohibition of national symbols, financing culture and picking national holidays come into question here (Kymlicka, 1995: 108). The merger, however, of already existing

strong national minority identities into the dominant national identity encounters strong resistance (Lijphart, 1979: 48-49), although the so much desired assimilation, propagated by the supporters of ethnically exclusive nation-stateness, was easy in the first stage of modernization. In societies with strong minority national identities oppression and forced assimilation might give the false impression of stability (Laponce, 1987: 199) but, in reality, they lead to tensions by creating a “cultural imperialism” in which the dominant group forces not only its language but also its historical and administrative interpretations onto the non-dominant groups (Young, 1990: 48-63). Since 2014, this has been happening openly in Ukraine, where, before that, but after the independence of 1991, deep social divisions, and blurred and permeable ethno-national and linguistic boundaries between ethnic Ukrainians and Russians long impeded the formation of a strong national identity (Zhurzhenko, 2014: 251-256).

Examples of Switzerland, Belgium, or Canada show that a common identity can be developed in multilingual countries if the national identity is not interconnected exclusively with one language, but emphasizes the common nature of the national identity and the recognition of the language groups is provided. If the state is propagating and enforcing, even in a covert way, the use of one official language at the expense of other languages such a shared national identity cannot be developed; the failure of the Soviet or the Yugoslav identities clearly showed this. If a multilingual nation-state strengthens the position of the official or majority language, it shall do it in a balanced way to protect multilingualism and multiculturalism, to preserve balance and social cohesion; this has been advised by international organizations and partners to Ukraine for several times, as we will see later.

Policies on territorial arrangements

If a national minority resides concentrated to a region of the nation-state, the protection of this territory against assimilation is of utmost importance for the minority (Laponce, 1987: 148-149). Attempts to protection, however, are seen as a danger to the territorial integrity of the state, therefore nation-states are mostly reluctant to implement territory-based solutions. European conventions, for instance the European Charter for Regional or Minority Languages or the Framework Convention for the Protection of National Minorities, provide us certain guidelines by connecting territories, languages and speakers and commend states to adopt legislation with respect to the preservation of these particularities. Further recommendations, documents of *soft law* nature, mostly adopted by the Parliamentary Assembly of the Council of Europe, go even further when they call for sharing knowledge and implementing best practices on autonomies, or self-governance, for minorities or regions where national minorities form a majority.¹ Similarly, in its Lund,

¹ For instance the PACE Resolution 1334 (2003), PACE Recommendation 1811 (2007), PACE Resolution 1832 (2011), PACE Resolution 1985 (2014).

and Ljubljana Recommendations, the High Commissioner on National Minorities of the OSCE deals with the question of autonomy, however, supporting autonomy is more an exception than a rule for the HCNM (Palermo, 2009: 658-659).

A nation-state not providing proper institutional framework for its minorities to protect themselves against assimilatory policies risks to lose its democratic legitimacy and might become a totalitarian state of the majority nation (Kusý, 2002: 99). National minority struggles for self-governance shall be seen thus as counter-measures against assimilatory policies of the state. If it is feasible, territorial autonomy, federalism or confederalism shall be applied with boundaries drawn so as to give speakers of the minority language(s) control over some provincial government(s) and—crucially—its education system that provides the necessary bulwark against the central state's nationalizing projects (Levy, 2007: 248). Autonomy is nor rare, neither extraordinary: the application of self-governance or the intention towards that is the fourth option for a national minority if we look at the co-existence of various ethnic groups within a single nation-state; the others might be emigration, assimilation, and isolation (Kymlicka, 2002: 343-349, 362).

In terms of national minority rights, the international community's approach has been put on individual rights since WWII. In the interwar period, several provisions allowed for collective rights, mainly in the Minority Treaties signed by Central European states winning the WWI. States mostly rejected collective rights even then: it was only in 1938 when the Czech-dominated first Czechoslovakia implemented its assignment for an autonomous Carpathian Ruthenia dating back to 1919; when the country was already in the process of falling apart. German and Hungarian minorities were oppressed in this interwar state, and Czechoslovakia showed interest to provide them autonomy only when Germany and Hungary reclaimed the territories with ethnic German and Hungarian majority. This was the case also for Hungary in 1918 and 1919. In the course of the breaking up of the multi-ethnic Hungarian state after WWI, the Parliament adopted laws designated to create autonomy for the Rusyn¹ and Slovak nations, and for ethnic German citizens of Hungary. All of these attempts proved to be unsuccessful to prevent the disintegration of the multi-ethnic states, both in the case of Hungary in 1918-1919, and Czechoslovakia in 1938-1939.

After WWII, the international community opted for individual rights, arguing that general human rights would resolve the situation of national minorities, and that collective rights represent a threat to the territorial integrity and the stability of the states. However, if we examine the relevant experiences, we find that it still is the collective approach which has proved to be successful in consolidating national

¹ Autochthonous Slavic nation residing mostly on Zakarpattia, Ukraine, but also in the neighbouring territories of Slovakia and Romania. The territory belonged to Hungary *de facto* until April 1919, and, *de iure* until June 1920.

minorities that form a majority on parts of a state, especially if that state declares itself a nation-state.

Autonomous institutions have been created mostly due to internal causes; international involvement is quite rare. For this, we could mention the example of the autonomy of the Åland Islands, where, after the decision of the League of Nations, the Åland Convention was signed on October 20, 1921, obligating Finland to provide an autonomy designed to preserve the Swedish nature of the archipelago. Similarly, the Dayton Agreement, signed on November 21, 1995, invented the ethnofederal Bosnia and Hercegovina based on three constituent peoples and two autonomous entities.¹ The international involvement in both cases originated in the interest of the international community to end a conflict and to secure regional stability.

Autonomous institutions are more likely to be elaborated after an internal agreement is reached, also often ending a conflict. This was the case for South Tyrol, where, although the Gruber-De Gasperi Agreement of 1946 between Austria and Italy recognized the right of the German minority to autonomy to preserve its cultural identity and customs; the implementation, however, took decades, involving terrorism (Steininger, 2017: 154-174) and international pressure too on Italy to resolve the *Südtirolfrage*. If we take other European examples, the appearance of violence is even more obvious: *The Troubles* in Northern Ireland were concluded by the Good Friday Agreement in 1998, the Basque ETA played a role in undermining the Franco regime and the new democratic Spanish state had to accept the idea of decentralization and the introduction of the system of autonomous communities. Violence occurred in Corsica, in the Republic of Moldova; while in Belgium, despite violence did not occur, the mere existence of the state came into question before the territory-based solutions to the ethnic problems were implemented.

Laws on national minorities in Ukraine

Due to its history, Ukraine is a multi-ethnic and multilingual country. The internationally recognized borders of Ukraine have been in place since 1954, when Nikita Khrushchev, the First Secretary of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union, transferred Crimea from the Russian Soviet Federative Socialist Republic (RSFSR) to the Ukrainian Soviet Socialist Republic (USSR). Before that, according to decisions taken in Moscow the territory of the USSR enlarged with former Southeast Poland: East Galicia and West Volhynia in 1939, with former Northeast Romania: Northern Bucovina, Hertsa and the Budjak in 1940, and with Transcarpathia (Zakarpattia) in 1945. These territories themselves were multi-ethnic, but the Ukrainian SSR had a multilingual population even before WWII, with a strong presence of Russian and Polish.

¹ The third unit, the condominium of Brčko District, was created later, in 1999.

According to the Ukrainian Constitution of 1996, the sole official language of the state is the Ukrainian, yet several surveys conducted after 1991 show that the Russian language have prevailed and remained the vernacular of a great part of the society, including parts of the political, social and economic elites. Before the 2010s, some third of the population used mainly another language than Ukrainian while the share of national minorities was around 20 percent; thus, a significant part of the Ukrainian nation also used another language, mostly Russian. This was the case although the Soviet state put a great effort on the homogenization of the Ukrainian people (Magocsi, 1978: 255-271). Their main concern, however, was tackling separatism based on regional identities and not the promotion of Ukrainian, especially not at the expense of the Russian language. This is partly why a widespread anxiety about the lack of a strong Ukrainian “national identity” appeared after the independence (Zhurzhenko, 2014). Undoubtedly, the inhabitants of Ukraine have a strong connection to the idea of Ukraine, yet what Ukraine means has been debated: interpretations on history and the desired social role of the Ukrainian language varied greatly in different regions of the country (Hrytsak, 1998: 269-272). After losing the regions where Russian identity is prevailing in 2014, a series of NGO and government organized initiatives appeared to foster national unification.¹

According to the last census conducted in Ukraine so far, that of 2001, Russian was mostly concentrated into urban settlements: 85.8 percent of the population of villages spoke Ukrainian and only 9.5 percent Russian, while in towns the ratio was 58.5 percent versus 39.5 percent (Tóth, 2016: 22). Ukrainian in Central, Eastern and Southern Ukraine, not counting Crimea, Donetsk, and Luhansk, however, meant to a great extent the Surzhyk dialect, a range of mixed sociolects of Ukrainian and Russian, used by some 11-18 percent of the populace of all Ukraine (Pataki, 2017: 209-210). If we look at the other ethnic groups of Ukraine, there are two major groups: the Bulgarian, Hungarian and Romanian ethnic minorities, living on the peripheries, have predominantly preserved their native tongue, while a great share of other minorities like Poles and Belorussians, living on the territories that belonged to Ukraine even before WWII, have switched to Ukrainian or Russian (Fedinec-Csernicskó, 2017: 281).

Before 2012, the use of languages was regulated by the law on languages in the USSR adopted in 1989, however, the status of the languages was a well-debated issue and a politically hot topic due to its connection to nation-building (Tóth, 2016, Arel, 2017-2018, Ambrus, 2019). Events after the Orange Revolution of 2004, and the 2008 reform concerning graduation of secondary schools showed clearly that some fractions of the political elite were frustrated with the social status of the Ukrainian even before 2014. The language law of 2012, however, acted in the opposite direction

¹ Makarenka, Olena (2017). Exchange programs dispel destructive myths, bridge east-west divide in Ukraine. July 4, 2017. <https://euromaidanpress.com/2017/07/04/exchange-programs-dispel-destructive-myths-bridge-divide-between-east-and-west-in-ukraine/>

recognizing 18 minority languages, including Rusyn,¹ and provided co-official status for all languages spoken by at least 10 percent of the population of a territorial unit—county, district, town, or village. Thus, Hungarian became co-official in Zakarpattia, Romanian in Chrenivtsi Oblast, Tatar in Crimea, and Russian in nine Oblasts.

The language law of 2012 was repelled by the Verkhovna Rada (Ukrainian Parliament) during the Maidan Revolution of 2014 fuelling social unrest in East Ukraine and Crimea and providing a pretext for Russia to invade Ukraine. It is noteworthy that even a significant part of the Ukrainian population disagreed with the decision of 2014, according to a survey of February 2015, 19 percent agreed the introduction of Russian as a second official language, and another 52 percent supported the use of Russian as a second official language where the population asked for it, and only 21 percent rejected it completely.² After losing the territories with majority Russian identity, the Ukrainian lawmaker started to carry out a legislation intending to strengthen the position of the Ukrainian at the expense of other languages (Fedinec-Csernicskó, 2017: 284-285). Since 2014, Ukrainian language policy has been focusing on the exclusion of Russian from public spheres. The actions, however, has a strong effect on other minority language speakers, too. It is to be noted, that even in the early 2000s, social climate was also hostile to minority language users sometimes (Beregszászi, 2004), and Ukrainian often was the sole language of official communication, especially in written (Beregszászi-Csernicskó, 2003). After the abolition of the language law, in May 2017, a new regulation on media was introduced increasing Ukrainian language content up to at least 75 percent in TV and radio programs, including private broadcasters.

The next major attack on minority rights came in September 2017, when the new “*Law on Education*” was adopted. By proclaiming Ukrainian the language of instruction in Art. 7, the law targeted public education institutions teaching in minority languages. This law was the first to introduce the distinction between indigenous peoples (корінні народи) and national minorities (національні меншини).³ Right to education in mother tongue was recognized only in preschool and primary (grades one to four) school, while for those minorities whose language is an official language of the EU,⁴ in secondary schools (grades five to twelve) the right to teach one or more disciplines in their language, alongside the Ukrainian, was also proclaimed. For other national minorities like Russians, Belorussians, such a right was

¹ An East Slavic language traditionally spoken in Zakarpattia and the neighbouring regions of Romania and Slovakia, unrecognized in Ukraine both before 2014 and after 2014 on the ground of regarding it to be a dialect of the Ukrainian.

² СТАВЛЕННЯ ДО СТАТУСУ РОСІЙСЬКОЇ МОВИ В УКРАЇНІ, 10 April 2015, <https://www.kiis.com.ua/?lang=ukr&cat=reports&id=517&page=5&t=10>

³ The Ukrainian legislator discriminates national minorities on the ground that the so-called indigenous peoples were formed on the territory of Crimea and have no kin-states to the contrary of other national minorities.

⁴ For instance, Bulgarian, Greek, Hungarian, Polish, Romanian, Slovakian.

not accorded, while for indigenous peoples the use of the mother tongue was ensured—at least on paper, since their homeland, Crimea was already under Russian occupation—in preschools, primary and secondary schools.

The international reaction to the law was harsh. The concerned EU member states protested, however, Ukraine managed to find a compromise with Bulgaria and Poland. Hungary, from where the harshest reaction came, also tried to reach a compromise, but the parallel talks between the Ukrainian Government and the Hungarian minority and the Hungarian Government turned out to be unsuccessful since Kyiv rejected the modification of the law, even according to the guidelines of the Venice Commission (Fiala-Butora, 2020: 246-247). Hungary wanted the restoration of the legal provisions in vigour prior to 2014, since it was worried that the devaluation of existing minority rights, once accepted in Ukraine, could be followed by other states having Hungarian minorities. Since no progress was achieved, Hungary started to block the NATO-Ukraine Commission on ministerial level, receiving criticism from the other NATO member states.

The law was criticized by international organizations, as well. On October 12, 2017, the Parliamentary Assembly of the Council of Europe (PACE) adopted a Resolution in which it expressed its concerns and called up Ukraine to take steps towards the integration, and not assimilation, of national minorities by taking measures to protect and promote the languages of national minorities when promoting the state language.¹ After the adoption of the law, Ukraine asked for the opinion of the Venice Commission² which delivered that on December 11, 2017.³ The Commission concluded that although the promotion of the state language is a legitimate interest, the specific law creates a disproportionate interference with the existing rights of persons belonging to national minorities (para 120). The legislation, according to the Venice Commission, diminishes the existing legal possibilities, and does not grant the right to education in the mother tongue only stipulates that such education is a possibility. The Commission called for the replacement of Art. 7 with a more a balanced and more clearly worded text which eliminates the discriminatory treatment of minority languages that are not official languages of the EU (para 125).

On March 5, 2018, the Council of Europe (CoE) published the Fourth Opinion on Ukraine of the Advisory Committee on the Framework Convention for the Protection of National Minorities'.⁴ The document covered a period of time before the adoption of the new law on education, yet it criticized the draft as being incompatible

¹ PACE Resolution 2189(2017) The New Ukrainian Law on Education: A Major Impediment to the Teaching of National Minorities' Mother Tongues, 12 October 2017.

² European Commission for Democracy through Law, is an advisory body of the Council of Europe.

³ Venice Commission, Ukraine – Opinion no. 902/2017 on the Provisions of the Law on Education of 5 September 2017, cdl-AD(2017)030, 11 December 2017.

⁴ ACFC Fourth Opinion on Ukraine – adopted on 10 March 2017, acfc/OP/iv(2017)002, Strasbourg, 5 March 2018.

with Art. 14 of the Framework Convention. In its December 12, 2017 report,¹ the Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR) also concluded that the law was more restrictive than the previous one, ran contrary to Ukraine's international obligations, discriminated against minority communities, and may result in increased tensions. In the Statement of the NATO-Ukraine Commission of October 31, 2019, even the NATO urged Ukraine to fully implement the recommendations and conclusions of the Venice Commission on the Law on Education, and Ukraine highlighted that it "is committed to doing so".²

The next piece of legislation targeting minority rights was the "*Law on the Supporting of the Functioning of the Ukrainian Language as the State Language*", adopted in April 2019. It made the use of Ukrainian compulsory in more than 30 spheres of public life, including education, culture, media, and health care institutions. The law generally met with popular support, however, a significant part of the population, especially in the East and South openly disagreed with the promotion of the Ukrainian, or declined to express opinion.³ The law does not regulate the use of minority languages, creating thus a legal uncertainty. The law also introduced the State Language Protection Commissioner to monitor compliance with the law, who from July 16, 2022, has the authority to impose fines.⁴ Furthermore, the law created the National Commission on State Language Standards to develop and approve the standards of the Ukrainian language, showing that alongside minority languages, also the Surzhyk became targeted by the state institutions.

This piece of legislation was again criticized heavily both internationally, and by the minority communities of Ukraine. According to the UN Human Rights Mission in Ukraine, the promotion of national identity and the official language is a legitimate objective, however, measures that seek to promote them must neither be coercive nor contrary to international human rights obligations, and the Ukrainian constitution.⁵ It also stated that language proficiency requirements must be proportionate and should not preclude participation of minority language-speakers in public life. With reference to the differential treatment between national minorities speaking an official language of the EU, and national minorities, whose languages are not official languages of the EU, the document called up the government to avoid violations of the right of equality before the law and of equal protection of the law. For private media, it urged free use

¹ Office of the unhchr, Report on the human rights situation in Ukraine 16 August to 15 November 2017, 12 December 2017.

² Point 6 of the statement. Statement of the NATO-Ukraine Commission, Kyiv, 31 October 2019, https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/official_texts_170408.htm

³ ПРЕС-РЕЛІЗИ ТА ЗВІТИ СТАВЛЕННЯ НАСЕЛЕННЯ УКРАЇНИ ДО ЗАКОНУ ПРО МОВУ, 29 July 2020, <https://www.kiis.com.ua/?lang=ukr&cat=reports&id=960&page=2&t=10>

⁴ The mayor of Harkiv was fined by the Commissioner on 24 November, 2022, for using non-state language in his public appeals. The mayor of Kharkiv must pay a fine for using the Russian language 24 November, 2022, <https://babel.ua/en/news/87451-the-mayor-of-kharkiv-must-pay-a-fine-for-using-the-russian-language>

⁵ Office of the UNHCR, Analytical Note on the Draft Law 'On Ensuring the Functioning of Ukrainian as the State language', 5 September 2019.

of language, including minority languages, while for public media, it advised that the languages of minorities must be provided with sufficient and proportionate space. In conclusion, the note urged the government *'to elaborate, without undue delay and in an inclusive consultative process, the (...) law on realization of the rights of indigenous peoples and national minorities of Ukraine in order to provide solid legal guarantees for the protection and use of all minority languages and to strike a balance between the goal of promoting the official language and the language rights of persons belonging to national minorities.'* (Recommendation to Point XIII)

The Venice Commission also examined the law, and published an opinion about it on December 9, 2019.¹ The Commission concludes that although it *'fully understands the need for the Ukrainian legislator to adopt measures to promote the use of Ukrainian as the State language'*, it *'has to be coordinated and adequately balanced with guarantees and measures for the protection of the linguistic rights of Ukraine's minorities, which may not be unduly diminished.'* The Commission clarifies that *'the State Language Law (...) fails to strike a fair balance between the legitimate aim of strengthening and promoting the Ukrainian language and sufficiently safeguarding minorities' linguistic rights'* and calls the Ukrainian Government to prepare without any unnecessary delay the Law on Minorities and to consider postponing until the adoption of the Law on Minorities the implementation of the State Language Law's provisions which are already in force; to revise the State Language Law to ensure its compliance with Ukraine's international commitments; to repeal the provisions of the Law providing for a differential treatment between the languages of the three categories of national minorities to the extent that the distinction between those languages is not based on an objective and reasonable justification; to safeguard the rights of linguistic minorities as well in order to promote a fair balance between the strengthening of the status and use of the State language and the protection of minority languages and to entrust the Commissioner for the Protection of the State Language, or another duly-constituted institution, with the responsibility to monitor the implementation of the legal provisions on the use of minority and indigenous languages.

On July 1, 2021, the Rada adopted the *"Law on the Indigenous Peoples of Ukraine"* that provides a framework for the protection of the rights of the indigenous peoples of the Crimean Peninsula, i.e. the Crimean Tatars, Karaites and Krymchaks, living *de facto* under Russian occupation. In 2001, their communities numbered 248,200; 1,196; and 406 people, respectively, according to the Ukrainian census. The law is a turning point for minority protection in Ukraine since it charts a path for laying claims to the lands in Crimea and girds the displaced minority groups with legitimate arguments to be raised before international fora about their repatriation (Sribniak 2021). The law largely echoes the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples by

¹ Venice Commission, Opinion on the Law on Supporting the Functioning of the Ukrainian language as the state language, CDL-AD(2019)032, 9 December, 2019.

guaranteeing their right to self-determination within Ukraine and self-government in matters relating to their internal affairs. The legal bodies of the indigenous peoples have advisory powers in forming a list of objects of indigenous peoples' cultural and religious heritage, restoration of historical toponymy, the inclusion of information on indigenous peoples in the school curriculum, and environmental protection in Crimea through an institutionalized dialogue with the state authorities. The law also imposes on the state the obligation to refrain from assimilation. It is telling that such a stipulation regarding to other national minorities has not been put in place, making them possible targets of assimilatory policies. Another problem is that the law is more of declarative nature, not only because Crimea is out of Ukrainian jurisdiction, but also because there is no regulation on the implementation and there are no guarantees that the transferred rights will not be revoked (Tóth, 2022: 10-14).

The so far last piece of legislation concerning the rights of national minorities is the Law on National Minorities, adopted on December 13, 2022. This law reinforces the limitations introduced earlier by the Law on Education or the Law on the Functioning of the Ukrainian Language as State Language and fails to address the criticisms raised internally or internationally. It is not a coincidence therefore, that the law was criticized by the representatives of the ethnic Hungarian minority,¹ the Romanian minority,² the Romanian Foreign Ministry,³ while the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Trade of Hungary addressed the OSCE High Commissioner on National Minorities,⁴ and the PACE asked the opinion of the Venice Commission.⁵ Similarly, Romanian⁶ and Hungarian Members of the European Parliament addressed the European Commission asking what it is able and willing to take in order to ensure the linguistic and educational rights of national minorities living in Ukraine, as required by the accession conditions and in accordance with the Copenhagen criteria.⁷

¹ A KMKSZ és az UMDSZ közös nyilatkozata Ukrajna nemzeti kisebbségeiről (közösségeiről) című törvénnyel kapcsolatban, 16 December 2022, <https://kmksz.com.ua/2022/12/16/a-kmksz-es-az-umdsz-koz-os-nyilatkozata-ukrajna-nemzeti-kisebbségeirol-kozossegeirol-cimu-torvennyel-kapcsolatban/>

² Noua lege a minorităților naționale din Ucraina, o dezamăgire pentru comunitatea românească. Problema educației în limba maternă, nerezolvată, 22 December 2022, <https://www.libertatea.ro/opinii/noua-lege-a-minoritatilor-nationale-din-ucraina-o-dezamagire-pentru-comunitatea-romaneasca-problema-educatiei-in-limba-materna-nerezolvata-4388900>

³ Comunicat de presă privind poziția MAE referitoare la adoptarea, de către Rada Supremă a Ucrainei, a Legii privind minoritățile naționale (comunitățile) din Ucraina, 22 December 2022, <https://www.mae.ro/node/60649>

⁴ Kérvényeztük az ukrán nemzeti kisebbségi törvény végrehajtásának elhalasztását, 14 March 2023, <https://kormany.hu/hirek/kervenyeztuk-az-ukran-nemzeti-kisebbségi-torveny-vegrehajtasanak-elhalasztasat>

⁵ No 1123/2023 - Ukraine - Opinion on the law on national minorities (communities). The adoption of the opinion is expected by June 2023. Documents by opinions and studies, https://www.venice.coe.int/WebForms/documents/by_opinion.aspx?v=ongoing&lang=EN

⁶ Protecting the rights of the Romanian community in Ukraine, 14 February 2023, https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/E-9-2023-000454_EN.html

⁷ Ensuring the rights of the Hungarian minority in Ukraine, 30 March 2023, https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/P-9-2023-001080_EN.html

Regions with ethnic minority majorities in Ukraine

There are areas within the internationally recognized borders of Ukraine where non-Ukrainian population form a majority. Ethnic Russians live mostly in Crimea, Donetsk, Luhansk and Zaporizhzhia regions, while the Bulgarian, Hungarian and Romanian speaking areas are located in Odessa, Zakarpattia and Chernivtsi regions, respectively. During the course of Ukraine's independence, some of them have advocated for internal self-determination, a special status within Ukraine.

In 1991, alongside with the referendum on independence, the residents of Crimea and Zakarpattia simultaneously voted on a special status for their regions within Ukraine; furthermore, by a popular vote, the mostly ethnic Hungarian residents of Berehove-Beregszász district also supported the creation of a Hungarian Autonomous Subregion (district) within Zakarpattia region. Regionalist movements occurred in Donetsk, Luhansk, Dnipro and Odessa too in the early 1990s (Goode, 2011: 139-140). The Verkhovna Rada in Kyiv, however, disregarded these popular referenda or wishes with the exception of Crimea, where the pressure was too high.

The status of the Russian-speaking peninsula was heavily debated in the 1990s. On May 5, 1992, the Supreme Council of the self-declared Crimean Republic declared independence depending on a referendum planned for August that year. It is to be stressed, that the challenging of the borders was not rare in the post-Soviet region then, even within the pre-first Chechen War Russia (Stern, 1994, Lundstedt, 2018). After months of negotiations, a compromise was reached in July 1992, providing an autonomous status and a special economic status for Crimea, which thus agreed to remain part of Ukraine. The Ukrainian readiness for compromise was strengthened by voices coming from Moscow that Crimea ought to be returned to Russia (Goode, 2011: 140). Following the compromise, the office of the President of Crimea was created in 1993, which was won by pro-Russian separatist Yuriy Meshkov in 1994 by popular vote. This led to increased tensions again, and finally, in 1995, the abolition of the post of President by the Verkhovna Rada, together with the Crimean Constitution of 1992. An interim period followed, ending in 1998 with the adoption of the second Constitution of Crimea—a year after the signing of the Russia-Ukraine Friendship Treaty in which Russia recognized the inviolability of the existing borders. The Crimean Constitution of 1998 had two aims, to allow for Ukraine to tackle ethnic Russian separatism in Crimea and maintain sovereignty over the peninsula, what ended in March 2014 with the illegal Russian occupation and annexation.

With parts of the state getting under foreign occupation, Ukraine had to come up with an interim solution. The situation was first regulated on April 15, 2014, by the Parliament which adopted the law No 1207-VII on *"Securing the Rights and Freedoms of Citizens and the Legal Regime on the Temporarily Occupied Territory of Ukraine"*. It ruled the right of entry and exit, guarantees of property rights and generally the rights of Ukrainian citizens under occupation, and also the functioning of the Ukrainian public

bodies. This was the time, when further parts of Ukraine, i.e. parts of Donetsk and Luhansk counties were driven out of Ukrainian control. This part of Ukraine had long been, and in April 2014 still was advocating for federalism within Ukraine. The official recognition of the Russian language as a second state language was highly popular there, and Russia was seen more favourable than in other Russian-speaking parts of Ukraine.¹ To distance themselves from Ukraine, on May 11, 2014, separatists held simultaneous referenda in Donetsk and Luhansk on independence. Russia initially had more ambitious goals, the creation of a counter-Ukraine, *Novorossiia* in the Eastern and Southern parts of Ukraine, without Crimea, yet it was abolished soon due to the lack of popular support (Shandra-Seely, 2019: 25-34). By the summer of 2014, even the holding of the secessionist territories came under question due to the successful counter-offensive of the Ukrainian Army. This resulted in the unofficial introduction of the Russian Army into Donbas in August 2014, since the Kremlin was willing to maintain control on these territories. With the covert Russian military involvement, Moscow started to cement the two ‘people’s republics’.

During the Minsk talks in 2014 and 2015, aiming a ceasefire, Donetsk and Luhansk were represented by their leaders at the time, although Ukraine stressed that their representation did not mean recognition. On September 16, 2014, the Verkhovna Rada adopted a bill “[O]n the Special Order of Local Self-government in Separate Regions of Donetsk and Luhansk Oblasts” which became Ukraine’s duty according to point 3 of Minsk I Agreement.² The law stipulated that Ukrainian legislation shall operate limited in the regions, i.e. with consideration of peculiarities determined by the law for the period of the introduced special order of local self-government.³ Practically, it allowed for rebel authorities to hold elections, to choose the language they use, and to exercise their own executive power, while local authorities got the right to create ‘people’s militias’.⁴ The law met with the will of the people, since according to a survey in 2019, the residents of secessionist-controlled Donbas preferred re-joining to Ukraine with a special autonomy over becoming part of Russia—with or without autonomy.⁵ Nevertheless, the number of areas regulated by the law was very restricted. Apart from Art. 4 that accorded free language use to all residents of the regions, the free use of Russian in public and private life, and allowed for public

¹ The Views and Opinions of South-Eastern Regions of Ukraine: April 2014. Kyiv International Institute of Sociology. <https://www.kiis.com.ua/?lang=eng&cat=reports&id=302&page=1&y=2014&m=4>

² № 1680-VI ЗАКОН УКРАЇНИ Про особливий порядок місцевого самоврядування в окремих районах Донецької та Луганської областей, 16 September 2014, <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/en/1680-18#Text>

³ The Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine adopted the Law “On the special order of local self-government in separate regions of Donetsk and Luhansk Oblasts” September 16, 2014. <https://www.rada.gov.ua/en/news/News/News/97818.html>

⁴ *Economic, Social and Territorial situation of Ukraine*. In-Depth Analysis, European Parliament, IP/B/REGI/NT/2014_2, November 17, 2014, [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/IDAN/2014/529089/IPOL_IDA\(2014\)529089_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/IDAN/2014/529089/IPOL_IDA(2014)529089_EN.pdf) 19.

⁵ Hood, L. (2019). Most people in separatist-held areas of Donbas prefer reintegration with Ukraine – new survey. 14 October 2019. <https://theconversation.com/most-people-in-separatist-held-areas-of-donbas-prefer-reintegration-with-ukraine-new-survey-124849>

bodies to use Russian and other languages within the limits of Ukrainian legislation and international commitments of Ukraine, the law failed to detail the content of the proposed special status. This clearly showed that the legislation rather targeted the international community than intended to settle the issue of the separatist regions (Fedinec, 2017: 59-62).

The law was set for a three-year-period since enactment, however, President Poroshenko issued a decree to the Verkhovna Rada to repeal the law after the illegal parliamentary and presidential elections of November 2, 2014. Yet, its first modification happened only in March 2015, when the legislator connected the application of the provisions of the law to the withdrawal of the illegal armed forces and the restoration of Ukrainian jurisdiction over the territory.¹ This, of course, was heavily criticized by both Russia and the secessionist regions. Obviously, the law could not have been implemented, since Ukraine has not been exercising power over the territories, yet the validity period of the law was prolonged continuously, last time in December 2021, thus its effect ceased on December 31, 2022. At the first renewal under his term, President Zelenskyy claimed that the extension was easier than to draft a new piece of legislation.²

Compering to the previous examples, a far less known situation is that of Zakarpattia. Zakarpattia itself is home to an ethnic Slavic population called Rusyn, with a considerable ethnic Hungarian minority on the border with Hungary. Rusyns historically have the intent to distance themselves from neighbouring ethnic groups (Calvi, 1999: 289-290). Rusyn identity was supported by the Hungarian administration between 1939 and 1944, to develop into a strong national identity, distinct from the Ukrainian one. Since 1945, Rusyn identity has not been recognized by the Soviet and Ukrainian authorities, with the exception of the period between 2012 and 2014, when the language was recognized as a minority language and not a dialect of Ukrainian.³ The modern language itself was codified in 1995, in Slovakia, where also a considerable Rusyn community lives (Magocsi, 1995).

In Zakarpattia, alongside with the popular support for the independence of Ukraine on December 1, 1991, two referenda were held simultaneously. One in the whole of Zakarpattia, and another in the Berehove-Beregszász district. The first one asked the populace whether they supported a special regime for Zakarpattia within Ukraine, and the second whether the inhabitants of Berehove-Beregszász district supported the creation of a Hungarian Autonomous District within the autonomous Zakarpattia of Ukraine. Both initiatives were supported by a great majority of the

¹ № 256-VIII ЗАКОН УКРАЇНИ Про внесення зміни до статті 10 Закону України "Про особливий порядок місцевого самоврядування в окремих районах Донецької та Луганської областей", 17 March 2015, <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/en/256-19#Text>

² The law on special order of local self-government in certain areas of Donbas may be extended for another year – President. December 10, 2019, <https://www.president.gov.ua/en/news/zakon-pro-osoblivij-poryadok-miscevogo-samovryaduvannya-v-ok-58821>

³ Today Rusyn language and identity are recognized in Hungary, Slovakia and Romania.

voters. In January 1992, the elected regional council asked the Verkhovna Rada to modify the Constitution to include the special status of both Zakarpattia and Berehove-Beregszász district (Dupka, 2004: 61, 167-176). This call was left unanswered, and the idea of ethnically defined regions was discarded by the adoption of the Ukrainian law on national minorities of 1992. This radicalized some Rusyn politicians in the early 1990s, without any tangible success so far, although there is clearly a regional popular support for the internal self-determination. What is even more worrying than the reluctance to deal with the question in Kyiv, is that the Rusyn political movement has become under the influence of the Kremlin since then, discrediting thus a just cause.¹

As mentioned, the Hungarian community also intended to create a region with special status where ethnic Hungarians form a majority, yet that was also neglected by the Ukrainian legislator. The community itself is a small one; it numbered some 130.000 people before 2022 (Tátrai et al, 2018). However, it is the double of the size of the German-speaking community of Belgium or almost the half of the German-speaking community of South Tyrol, Italy, and equals to the population of autonomous Gagauzia in Moldova. According to the Ukrainian census of 2001, ethnic Hungarians formed a majority of 76 percent in the Berehove-Beregszász district, yet ethnic Hungarians also made up 33 percent of the Uzhhorod, 25 percent of the Vynohradiv, and 12 percent of the Mukachevo districts. These territories were all bordering to the Berehove-Beregszász district thus the Hungarian community formed a continuous area 'gerrymandered' into four districts. The community has several times asked for the merging these ethnic Hungarian inhabited parts into a single one and also called for regional autonomy by the creation of a Hungarian Autonomous District. They also urged for the creation of an electoral district where ethnic Hungarians form a majority, as it existed between 1997 and 2002, to have the chance to elect an MP to the Verkhovna Rada in Kyiv.

However, these requests have not been respected, and even the administrative reform of 2020 failed to address the issue, despite creating larger districts than the previous ones. The reform merged the ethnic Ukrainian-majority Vynohradiv district into the ethnic Hungarian-majority Berehove-Beregszász district but failed to incorporate the parts of Uzhhorod and Mukachevo districts with ethnic Hungarian majority with the exception of two villages. Therefore, according to the data of 2001, the new Berehove-Beregszász district has become of ethnic Ukrainian majority—42.1 percent Hungarian and 52.8 percent Ukrainian—, while the share of ethnic Hungarians decreased in both the Uzhhorod and the Mukachevo districts to 13.9 and

¹ Гибридная война: этнический фактор русинов Закарпатья. Аналитика ИС, 21 April 2016, https://svetlovodsk.com.ua/8964-sbu.html?fb_comment_id=849331198505739_849332888505570, Україна в лещатах російських спецслужб, 25 December 2011, <https://www.radiosvoboda.org/a/24433107.html>

5.9 percent respectively. Out of the 75 new *hromadas* (municipalities), 64 is of Ukrainian, 10 of Hungarian¹ and 1 of ethnic Romanian majority (Molnár, 2021).²

The most recent development in this regard is also alarming: on May 8, 2023, Presidential Office advisor Mykhailo Podolyak said that after the liberation, Crimea may lose its autonomy, since for a unitary state, autonomy is a dangerous path.³ Considering the European experiences and the history of Ukraine, however, such a movement would not lead to increased stability in Ukraine had it regain control over Crimea with its population of majority Russian identity.

Conclusions

Ukraine has been carrying out a nation-state building by the book, known from the 19th and 20th centuries. Due to the war, the popular support to this is given, since the ratio of the Ukrainian citizens declaring themselves ethnic Russians has radically diminished after Crimea, Donetsk and Luhansk were driven out of Ukrainian control. The war has a long-lasting effect on interethnic relations, according to a survey carried out by the Kyiv International Institute of Sociology (KIIS) in early 2023, the attitude of the society is largely hostile against ethnic Russians.⁴ A previous KIIS survey showed that it is the Russian ethnicity that Ukrainians reject, not the language itself.⁵ The reason for this could be that a significant part of the society still keeps speaking Russian, although feels Ukrainian.

Since 2014, the position of the Ukrainian has been strengthened by the legislator unilaterally and at the expense of other languages. This move has been criticized several times both internally and externally, by kin-states and international organizations, without having much effect on Ukraine. Argumentations that it might not be timely to address minority problems at the time of war are false, since the problem has been exaggerated by the Ukrainian legislator exactly during such times. It is more reasonable therefore to say that the Ukrainian legislator uses the chance of turbulence to foster nation-state building, hoping that laws restricting minority rights and contradicting the state's constitutional order and international commitments will go largely unnoticed and uncriticised due to the moral support for Ukraine in its defensive war against Russia.

¹ 7 out of the 10 *hromadas* of the Berehove-Beregszász district are of ethnic Hungarian majority, while 3 *hromadas* of the Uzhhorod district are also of Hungarian majority.

² For the Romanian minority in Zakarpattia, the administrative reconfiguration was a success, since they form a majority of 86.7 percent in the Solotvyno-Slatina *hromada* where some 94.5 percent of the ethnic Romanians of Zakarpattia reside.

³ Crimea may lose its autonomy after liberation, Podolyak says. 8 May, 2023, <https://english.nv.ua/nation/crimea-may-lose-its-autonomy-after-liberation-podolyak-says-50323040.html>

⁴ Як в Україні змінилось ставлення до етнічних росіян і які тенденції переважають? 2 April 2023, <https://hromadske.radio/podcasts/my-ie-buly-y-budem-informatsiynny-maraton/yak-v-ukraini-zminylos-stavlennia-do-etnichnykh-rosiian-i-iaki-tendentsii-perevazhaiut>

⁵ СТАВЛЕННЯ ДО БІЖЕНЦІВ, ВНУТРІШНЬО-ПЕРЕМІЩЕНИХ ОСІБ, ДО РОСІЙСЬКОМОВНИХ ГРОМАДЯН ТА ДО ДЕЯКИХ ІНШИХ КАТЕГОРІЙ НАСЕЛЕННЯ УКРАЇНИ, 30 March, 2023, <https://www.kiis.com.ua/?lang=ukr&cat=reports&id=1218&page=1>

However, if we look into the depth of the problem, we can see that unresolved problems of the national minorities create vulnerability. This was falsely usurped by Russia when moving against Ukraine in 2014, and also when attacking it openly in 2022. Other examples teach us that resolving minority issues could be done only by mutual respect and openness. It is always the state that has to offer a dialogue and show commitment in exchange of the recognition of the borders by the national minority. It is more the duty of a country building a nation-state. European cases show that force applied on minorities often result in conflict, and the resolution of the conflict often requires territory-based power sharing. Where such institutions are in place, conflict and vulnerability decrease and social cohesion grows. This leads to better understanding and a more peaceful coexistence, both within the state and on international level. This is the lecture Ukraine, and other Central European countries shall learn.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Acton Lord /John Emerich Edward Dalberg-Acton/ (1862). Nationality. The Home and Foreign Review (July 1862). <https://www.panarchy.org/acton/nationality.html>

Alfredsson G. (1997). Autonomy and Human Rights. In. Lise Lyck (ed.). *Constitutional and Economic Space of the Small Nordic Jurisdictions*, Nordiska Institutet För Regionalpolitiska Forskning, p. 34-47.

Ambrus Nikolett (2019). Az ukrán nyelvpolitika fejlődése és átalakulása 1991-től napjainkig. In. Dabis Attila. *Kisebbségi jogok érvényesülése a Kárpát-medencében 2019*. Budapest, Kisebbségi Jogvédő Intézet, p. 11-57.

Arel Dominique (2017-2018). The Battle for Ukrainian: A Comparative Perspective. In. *Harvard Ukrainian Studies* 35(1-4), 233-263.

Beregszászi Anikó, Csernicskó István (2003). A magyar nyelv használatának lehetőségei Kárpátalján de jure és de facto. In. Nádor Orsolya, Szarka László (Eds.). *Nyelvi jogok, kisebbségek, nyelvpolitika Kelet-Közép-Európában*, Akadémiai Kiadó, Budapest, p. 110-119.

Beregszászi Anikó (2004). Megfélemlített anyanyelvhasználat. In. Beregszászi Anikó, Csernicskó István. *...itt mennyit ér a szó? – Írások a kárpátaljai magyarok nyelvhasználatáról*, PoliPrint, Ungvár, p. 90-96.

Calvi Luca (1999). The Carpatho-Rusyn Particularity as a Model of Borderland Identity: Some Reflections for Going Beyond the Nations and Looking for Regions in Future Central Europe. In. Gehl Hans, Ciubotă Viorel. *Relații interetnice în zona de contact româno-maghiaro-ucraineană din secolul al XVIII-lea până în prezent*. Editura Muzeului Sătmărean, Cluj Napoca, p. 286-299.

Connor W. (1979). Ethnonationalism in the First World: The Present in Historical Perspective. In. Esman, M. J. (ed.). *Ethnic Conflict in the Western World*. Cornell University Press, Ithaca–London, p. 19-45.

Dupka György (2004). *Autonómia-törekvések Kárpátalján*, Intermix Kiadó, Ungvár-Budapest.

Economic, Social and Territorial situation of Ukraine. In-Depth Analysis, European Parliament, IP/B/REGI/NT/2014_2, November 17, 2014, [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/IDAN/2014/529089/IPOL_IDA\(2014\)529089_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/IDAN/2014/529089/IPOL_IDA(2014)529089_EN.pdf)

Fedinec Csilla (2017). Kárpátalja magyarsága a második Majdan után. In. Dabis Attila. *Kisebbségi jogok érvényesülése a Kárpát-medencében 2017*. Kisebbségi Jogvédő Intézet, Budapest, p. 59-72.

Fedinec Csilla, Csernicskó István (2017). A 2017-es ukrajnai oktatási kerettörvény: a szöveg keletkezéstörténete és tartalma, In. *Regio*, 25(3), p. 278-300.

Fiala-Butora János (2020). The Controversy Over Ukraine's New Law on Education: Conflict Prevention and Minority Rights Protection as Divergent Objectives? In. *European Yearbook of Minority Issues Online*, Brill | Nijhoff, Leiden, p. 233-261.

Goode J. Paul (2011). *The Decline of Regionalism in Putin's Russia*, Routledge, London and New York

Hrytsak Yaroslav (1998). National Identities in Post-Soviet Ukraine: The Case of Lviv and Donetsk. In. *Harvard Ukrainian Studies* 22, p. 263-281.

Kymlicka Will (1995). *Multicultural Citizenship*, Oxford University Press, Oxford.

Kymlicka Will (2002). *Contemporary Political Philosophy: An Introduction*, Oxford University Press, Oxford.

Kymlicka Will, Bashir Bashir (2012). *The Politics of Reconciliation in Multicultural Societies*. Oxford University Press, Oxford.

Kusý Miroslav (2002). *A magyarkérdés Szlovákiában*, Kalligram Kiadó, Pozsony.

Laponce Jean A. (1987). *Languages and Their Territories*, University of Toronto Press, Toronto-Buffalo-London.

Levy Jacob T. (2007). Language Rights, Literacy, and the Modern State. In. Will Kymlicka, Patten Allen (Eds.). *Language Rights and Political Theory*. Oxford University Press, Oxford, p. 230-249.

Lijphart Arend (1979). Political Theories and the Explanation of Ethnic Conflict in the Western World: Falsified Predictions and Plausible Postdictions. In. Esman Milton J. (Ed.). *Ethnic Conflict in the Western World*, Cornell University Press, Ithaca-London, p. 46-64.

Magocsi Paul Robert (1978). *The Shaping of a National Identity, Subcarpathian Rus', 1848-1948*. Cambridge, Massachusetts, Harvard University Press, London.

Magocsi Paul Robert (1995). A new Slavic language is born. In. *Revue des études slaves* 67(1), 238-240.

May Stephen (2007). Misconceiving Minority Language Rights: Implications for Liberal Political Theory. In. Will Kymlicka, Patten Allen (Eds.). *Language Rights and Political Theory*. Oxford University Press, Oxford, p. 123-152.

Molnár D. István (2021). Kárpátalja lakosságának területi eloszlása az újonnan kialakított közigazgatási rendszer tükrében. In. Molnár D. Erzsébet, Molnár Ferenc. *Társadalomtudományi tanulmányok*. II. RF KMF – “RIK-U” Kft, Beregszász-Ungvár, p. 239-254.

Palermo Francesco (2009). When the Lund Recommendations Are Ignored: Effective Participation of National Minorities through Territorial Autonomy. In. *International Journal on Minority and Group Rights* 16(4), 653-663.

Pataki István (2017). A 2012-es ukrán nyelvtörvény és az új nyelvtörvény tervezeteinek összehasonlító elemzése. In. Dabis Attila. *Kisebbségi jogok érvényesülése a Kárpát-medencében 2017*. Kisebbségi Jogvédő Intézet, Budapest, p. 201-216.

Requejo Ferrán (2007). *Federalismo plurinacional y pluralismo de valores – El caso español*, Centro de estudios políticos y constitucionales, Madrid.

Shandra Alya, Seely Robert (2019). *The Surkov Leaks – The Inner Workings of Russia’s Hybrid War in Ukraine*. London, Royal United Services Institute (RUSI).

Sribniak Olha (2021). ECMI Minorities Blog. Native Others: What Implications Does the Law on Indigenous Peoples Have for Ukraine’s Indigenous Population? <https://www.ecmi.de/infocchannel/detail/ecmi-minorities-blognative-others-what-implications-does-the-law-on-indigenous-peoples-have-for-ukraines-indigenous-population>

Steininger Rolf (2017). *Südtirol – Vom Ersten Weltkrieg bis zur Gegenwart*. Haymon TB, Innsbruck-Wien.

Stern Jessica Eve (1994). Moscow Meltdown: Can Russia Survive? In. *International Security* 18(4), p. 40-65.

Tátrai Patrik, Molnár József, Kovály Katalin, Eröss Ágnes (2018). A kárpátaljai magyarok lélekszáma és a népesedésüket befolyásoló tényezők a SUMMA 2017 felmérés alapján. In. *Kisebbségi Szemle* 3(3), p. 7-31.

Tóth Mihály (2016). Az anyanyelvhasználathoz való jog az Európai Unión kívül: az ukránjai példa. In. *Acta Humana* 4(3), p. 19-31.

Tóth Mihály (2022). Az ukránjai kisebbségek jogi helyzete: jogalkotás és joggyakorlat a kisebbségvédelmi elvárásokkal szemben. In. *Kisebbségvédelem* 3(2), p. 7-43.

Young Iris Marion (1990). *Justice and the Politics of Difference*. Princeton, Princeton University Press.

Zhurzhenko Tatiana (2014). A Divided Nation? Reconsidering the Role of Identity Politics in the Ukraine Crisis. In. *Die Friedens-Warte* 89(1-2), p. 249-267.